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EFFECT OF RESIDUAL STRESSES ON TORQUE BEHAVIORS OF COMPOSITES LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

A determination of residual stresses on composites laminate by the incremental hole-drilling method is described in this paper. Different levels of residual stresses were introduced on laminate by using different cooling conditions on process cycle. The new measurement technique makes it possible to determine the in-depth distribution of the residual stresses within the laminate and more particularly on the interface between adjacent plies. The results show that the level of the residual stresses evolves appreciably with the cooling conditions and the stresses are not constant inside a same ply. After that, the influence of the residual stresses on behavior in torsion of laminated composite plates carbon-epoxy was investigated in the case of a torque loading. During these tests, the acoustic emission technique is used in order to investigate the damage initiation. This study indicates that the influence of the residual stresses on the torsion behavior is relatively weak and the damage initiation appears very early for the three cooling conditions.

KEYWORDS : Composites laminate, Residual stresses, Acoustic emission, Torsion loading

INTRODUCTION

Composite plates are not usually used to undergo torque loading. However in many cases, a " parasitic " loading such as torsion can damage the structure. The adding of a torque loading to a significant state of residual stresses can be the source of a early degradation of the structure. It's the raison why it's is very important to determine the influence of the residual stresses on behaviour of plates under torsion loading. The processing of composites laminate needs the application of complex cycles of temperature and pressure. During these cycles, many chemical and thermal reactions proceed within material and internal stresses appear. These stresses can be the origin of damages, such as micro-cracking and micro-delamination, which can be the cause of a degradation of the structure [1]. There are many techniques to highlight and to determine the residual stresses [2]. In the case of composite laminate, the most popular of these techniques is the measurement of the curvature on unsymmetrical laminates. S.R

White and H.T Hahn [3] used this technique to study the influence of the forming process parameters on the development of the residual stresses during the cure cycle. Contrary to the majority of the others, this technique is very employed, relatively simple and direct. But, this method doesn't give information about the stress distribution within the laminate. The classical theory of the laminate [4] also allows the study of the residual stresses.

In this study, the residual stresses will be determined by the incremental hole-drilling method. With this new method we can determine the in the depth profile of the stresses on the laminate by considering that the stresses are not constant within a same ply.

RESIDUAL STRESSES DETERMINATION

The hole-drilling method use a strain-gage rosette applied on the surface of specimen. A hole is drilled into the plate through the center of the rosette. The hole causes a redistribution of strains to occur near the hole, which can be detected and measured by the strain gages. These experimental strain datum can be related to residual stresses in the material at the hole location.

Originally, the hole-drilling method with strain gages was proposed for isotropic and homogeneous materials with an aim of determining the uniform residual stresses on all the depth of the material [5]. Bert [6] and Lake [7] extended this method to orthotropic materials by introducing new calibration coefficients. But with these various methods, only of the uniform stresses in-depth can be given. In the composite laminate, the residual stresses are no constants in the depth and thus the old methods is unsuited. It's for this reason that the incremental hole drilling method was developed [8][9]. The principle of determination remains the same one as in the case of the emerging hole but here drilling is made in an incremental way. In many cases, this method gives access to a high stress gradient.

The experimental procedure is very simple. Indeed, for each increment of drilling " n ", the strains ϵ_{in} ($i=1..3$) are measured on the surface. When drilling is finished, the principal residual stresses $\sigma_{1(n)}$ et $\sigma_{2(n)}$ are determined for each increment by using the measured strains and calibration coefficients. These coefficients depend primarily on the strain gages position, on the characteristics of material and the geometry of the bored hole and they are determined by using finite element analysis.

The first step of the method is the measurement of the "disturb" strains. For that, a 45° strain-gage rosette was placed on 0°, 135° and 270° in surface of the laminate (figure 1).

Fig.1 Rosette gages instrumentation

The depth of each increment was choosing so that drilling arrives alternatively either at the half thickness of each ply or at the interface between two plies. After each drilling increment, the cutter is withdrawn out of the hole and the strains are measured by a computerized data acquisition system.

Equation 1 presents the model, which was adopted to establish the existing relation between the residual stresses and the radial strains measured on the surface. We use an Fourier expansion solution as :

$$\mathbf{e}_n(\mathbf{q}) = A_{in}(\mathbf{s}_{1hi} + \mathbf{s}_{2hi}) + (\mathbf{s}_{1hi} - \mathbf{s}_{2hi})(B_{in} \cos 2\mathbf{q} + C_{in} \sin 2\mathbf{q}) \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{1hi}, \sigma_{2hi}$: principal stresses in lay 'i'

A_{in}, B_{in}, C_{in} : calibration coefficients

θ_i : angle between gage 1 and the first principal direction

The strain measurement by the 3 gages makes it possible to determine the three unknown factors of the problem $\sigma_{1hi}, \sigma_{2hi}$ et θ_i for each increment of drilling.

After the n^{th} increment, the total depth is h_n and equation (1) becomes :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_n^1 &= A_{in}(\mathbf{s}_{1hi} + \mathbf{s}_{2hi}) + (\mathbf{s}_{1hi} - \mathbf{s}_{2hi})(B_{in} \cos 2\mathbf{q} + C_{in} \sin 2\mathbf{q}) \\ \mathbf{e}_n^2 &= A_{in}(\mathbf{s}_{1hi} + \mathbf{s}_{2hi}) + (\mathbf{s}_{1hi} - \mathbf{s}_{2hi})(B_{in} \cos 2(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{a}) + C_{in} \sin 2(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{a})) \\ \mathbf{e}_n^3 &= A_{in}(\mathbf{s}_{1hi} + \mathbf{s}_{2hi}) + (\mathbf{s}_{1hi} - \mathbf{s}_{2hi})(B_{in} \cos 2(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{b}) + C_{in} \sin 2(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{b})) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

After that and for each increment of drilling, we obtain equation (3) by inverting the system of equations according to :

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{s}_{1hn} &= \frac{\mathbf{e}_n^l (A_{nn} + B_{nn} \sin 2\mathbf{q}_i - C_{nn} \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i) - \mathbf{e}_n^2 (A_{nn} - B_{nn} \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i - C_{nn} \sin 2\mathbf{q}_i)}{2A_{nn}B_{nn}(\sin 2\mathbf{q}_i + \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i) + 2A_{nn}C_{nn}(\sin 2\mathbf{q}_i - \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i)} \\
\mathbf{s}_{2hn} &= \frac{-\mathbf{e}_n^l (A_{nn} - B_{nn} \sin 2\mathbf{q}_i + C_{nn} \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i) + \mathbf{e}_n^2 (A_{nn} + B_{nn} \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i + C_{nn} \sin 2\mathbf{q}_i)}{2A_{nn}B_{nn}(\sin 2\mathbf{q}_i + \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i) + 2A_{nn}C_{nn}(\sin 2\mathbf{q}_i - \cos 2\mathbf{q}_i)} \quad (3) \\
\tan 2\mathbf{q}_i &= \frac{2C_{nn}(\mathbf{e}_n^3 - \mathbf{e}_n^2) - B_{nn}(-2\mathbf{e}_n^2 + \mathbf{e}_n^l + \mathbf{e}_n^3)}{C_{nn}(-2\mathbf{e}_n^l + \mathbf{e}_n^2 + \mathbf{e}_n^3) + B_{nn}(\mathbf{e}_n^3 - \mathbf{e}_n^l)}
\end{aligned}$$

In order to calculate the residual stresses, we must determine the calibration coefficients. They depend on the strain gages geometry, on the position of layer 'i' and on the depth of the hole. These coefficients do not depend on the applied loading on the structure. For a given material, it is enough to determine them only once. Figure 2 presents, for the three cooling conditions (A : fast cooling, B : normal cooling, C : slow cooling), the evolution of strains measured on the surface after each drilling increment.

Fig. 2 Micro strain in surface, ϵ_1 (0°) et ϵ_2 (135°)

Although these results give a first idea of the relative influence of each cooling condition. They do not enable in any case to obtain the conclusions for the level and the distribution of the residual stresses within material. However, these results confirm the role of the border $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and let foresee that the stresses are not constant within a same ply. Having determined the calibration coefficients numerically and knowing the strains generated by drilling, it is now enough to determine the residual stresses. Figures 3 presents the in-depth profile of the residual stresses determined by equation 3.

Fig.3 *sl*

The results show that the general level of the residual stresses increases with the cooling rate. The fast cooling generates a level of stress higher than that generated by two other cooling conditions. It is observed that the stress σ_1 changes sign at the crossing of frontiers between the plies 0° and 90° . The plies 0° subjected a compressive stress whereas the plies 90° are subjected by a tensile stress. But the first drilling increments (in 0° plies), the residual stresses are almost identical for the 3 cooling conditions. The great difference appears when the ply orientation changes their direction.

For the 3 cooling conditions, the highest residual stresses level is at the border $0^\circ/90^\circ$. Near the surface, out of the influence of the border, the level of stresses remains relatively low. After the crossing of frontiers $0^\circ/90^\circ$, the level of residual stresses becomes again weaker. The explanation concerning the influence of this border remains valid for the 90° plies.

For the first increment the stress is about -35Mpa, which is close to the values determined by the laminate classical theory (~ -40 Mpa). On the other hand, for the fourth increment, we note that the stress increases appreciably, which is explained by the proximity of the border $0^\circ/90^\circ$. In this zone the stress level is affected by the cooling conditions. Indeed, it is observed that the conditions A and B generate high levels of stress (~ -120 Mpa and -70 Mpa) whereas it remains constant in the case C. Also, the values of high stress was obtained to the border (~ 150 Mpa), and this for the three cooling conditions, whereas this stress level becomes again relatively low for the following increment (~ 20 MPa). This stress profile confirms the dominating role of the ply orientation in the development of the residual stresses and also the influence of the cooling conditions. Comparing with the values determined by classical calculations, the values obtained here are higher, particularly on the level of the border $0^\circ/90^\circ$. On the one hand, this difference can be in fact explained that the classical theory does not take into account a certain number of defects existing within material, and on the other hand, for the significant sensitivity of our method. In fact, the experimental measurement of the deformations generated by the drilling of the hole is delicate especially when the bottom of the hole approaches the border $0^\circ/90^\circ$.

TORQUE TEST

On the first part of this study, we determined and compared the residual stress field generated by different curing cycles. Knowing that the 3 series of fabricated laminates have different levels of residual stresses, we endeavoured in this second part to determine the influence of residual stresses on the mechanical behaviour in torque loading. In parallel, the damage initiation during the torque solicitation was studied by using the technique of acoustic emission. The various specimens was cut off from the laminates presented above. Their dimensions are 160×15× 1mm.

Each specimen was instrumented by a receptor of acoustic emission. The specimens were loaded in rotation control at a constant rate of 20°/min in order to better see the occurrence of the damage mechanisms.

Figure 4 shows a experimental curve of torsion using acoustic emission technique. The damage initiation is determined by the starting of the acoustic emission. We employ here cumulated counting.

Fig 4. Torsion test and acoustic emission technique

The table 1 presents the results obtained for each cooling condition. For each cooling condition, five tests have been made.

Cooling types	Fracture angle (°)	Fracture torque (N.m)	Angle of damage initiation (°)	Torque of damage initiation (N.m)
Fast (A)	135.90 ± 18.17	2.27 ± 0.05	3.70 ± 0.28	0.03 ± 0.01
Normal (B)	122.90 ± 7.07	2.11 ± 0.13	3.30 ± 0.20	0.03 ± 0.005
Slow (C)	126.20 ± 11.88	2.16 ± 0.15	3.6 ± 0.45	0.03 ± 0.004

Table 1. Results of torque test

The results show that even if the level of residual stresses within the various specimens are not identical, it doesn't have influence on behavior in torsion. Indeed, the torque moment and the rotation angle are almost identical for three cooling conditions. The difference between the three conditions do not exceed 8%. It is noted that the damage initiation appears very early for the three cooling conditions and that the final fracture arrives appreciably for the same angle of torsion.

These results must be compared with those obtained in our preceding study [10] concerning the influence of the residual stresses in the case of tensile test. The precedent study on tensile loading have shown that the level of residual stresses plays a significant role on the fracture and the damage initiation.

CONCLUSION

A new method of measurement of the residual stresses was presented. We can determine various levels of residual stresses within laminates having undergone various cycles of polymerization. The results show that the level of residual stresses evolves appreciably with the used cooling rate. The second part of this study showed that the residual stresses do not play a significant role on the torsion behavior. This conclusion differs with an other study which proves that residual stresses play an important role on the tensile behavior.

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